

Data* from: Strengthening mechanism in Al-Cu-Li alloy processed by friction consolidation followed by high-pressure torsion

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General Information

This repository contains all raw data and processed fitting outputs associated with the research published in:

E. Mathew et al., *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* (2025).

DOI: [10.1016/j.jallcom.2025.185374](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2025.185374)

The dataset is organized according to the characterization techniques used in the study and the analysis workflow related to the strengthening mechanisms. Each folder contains the corresponding raw data referenced in the publication. The FC, SAXS, hardness, TEM, and SEM experiments were conducted at Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon. The XRD measurements were performed at Hamburg University of Technology, and the HPT processing was carried out at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology. The overall investigation and coordination of the research were performed at Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon.

Folder Structure

- **XRD/**
Contains raw X-ray diffraction (XRD) data. A `README.txt` file is included with additional information about the sample and processing conditions.
- **SAXS/**
Contains reduced detector images from the small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) measurements. Two subfolders are included:
 - **FC/** – Contains reduced SAXS images, along with a `fit/` subfolder that includes the fitting results, such as volume fraction and radius information.
 - **FC+HPT/** – Contains reduced SAXS images and a corresponding `fit/` subfolder. A `README.txt` file is provided with additional details, including the measurement positions (five positions), file naming conventions, and the contents of the `fit/` folder.

*This data is shared open access under the CC BY 4.0 license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

- **TEM/**
Contains raw transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images.
- **SEM/**
Contains raw scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images. Two subfolders are included:
 - **Only_HPT/** – SEM images of samples processed solely by high-pressure torsion (HPT).
 - **FC/** – SEM images of samples processed by friction consolidation to check pores.
- **FC_process_parameter/**
Contains raw force, rotation, and temperature data from the friction consolidation process.
- **Hardness_data/**
Contains raw hardness data.

Citation

If you use any part of this dataset, please cite the associated publication:

E. Mathew et al., *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* (2025).

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